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Macroeconomic Determinants of Remittance Inflow in Nepal

ADITYA POKHREL
ASSISTANT DIRECTOR

Nepal Rastra Bank

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the relationship of the remittance inflow with its macroeconomic determinants using the Johannsson Co Integration approach for the period of 1993-2019. The results based on the Johannsson Co Integration procedure reveal that there exists cointegration with the long-run causal relationship among the remittance inflow, domestic rate of interest (on savings), inflation, and exchange rate. The coefficient of inflation and exchange rate was positive to the remittance inflow, however, the domestic rate on savings was found to be negatively related to the remittance inflow. In addition, the vector error correction model suggests that the system was correcting towards equilibrium at 72.3 percent per year which means that it takes 1.38 years to fully recover from the short-run disequilibrium and the long-run model obtained was stable with significant diagnostic tests and stability tests. Finally, the remittance inflow was significantly impacting to rise in inflation and the value of the exchange rate implying that effective policy stances to be taken to avert the remittance inflow towards fueling the productive activities in the country.

KEYWORDS

remittance inflow, cointegration, vector error correction model, stability.

JEL CLASSIFICATION

F24, F4

1. Introduction

For a few decades, Remittance inflow has been the source of income in many of the low middle-income countries and some developing countries as well. Chettri, KC, and Dhakal (2020) mentioned that Nepal is the fourth largest country to have a remittance as a percentage of a GDP in the whole world and the first one is Tonga. Nepal ranks 19th position on the top remittance-receiving countries in the world (Chettri et.al, 2020). Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, the remittance inflows increased by 12.6 percent to 870.94 billion in the review period against a decrease of 3.5 percent in the same period of the previous year (Nepal Rastra Bank [NRB], 2021). Chamlagain (2015) stated that the remittance in Nepal and Labor force in Nepal are very important driving forces for economic growth both in the long and short term. It was further stated that Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Foreign aid also do not impact output growth in both the short and long run. Further, Pant (2017) also mentioned that the depreciation of the Nepalese currency concerning the value of a dollar has a positive impact on remittances. In the same way, the economic activity of India, Gulf nations, and advanced economies also have been found to actively affect the remittance inflow in Nepal.

In the study conducted by Gaudel (2007) it was revealed that due to the prevailing poverty of Nepal, a large portion of the remittance income goes on consumption, capital formation, and doing business enjoying a minimal share.

The shortage of labor due to emigration keeps land barren, reduces agricultural productivity, and ultimately requires importing much and hence deteriorates the economy. In addition to this, a rise in disposable income may be spendthrift or luxury and branded items, replacing the consumption and production of the local goods. Remittance had played several positive roles in Nepal to lessen the iconic reduction of poverty and unemployment, maintaining foreign exchange reserves, and correcting the Balance of Payments. Chettri et al. (2020) further detailed in the study that there was a positive and significant correlation found between GDP and Remittance inflow per year at a 10% level of significance. Remittance as compared with the percentage of GDP and share of agriculture, forestry, and fishing were negatively and significantly correlated. As the volume of remittance is increased rapidly, the dependency of people on remittance is increasing and the economy is also gradually becoming consumption-oriented. The problem of the labor shortage in agriculture, as well as non-agricultural areas, stood as a genuine problem as active youths are involved in foreign employment (Chettri et al., 2020). During the past 15 years, the remittance inflow of Nepal has surged so high and has become the driving force for the migrants to apply for foreign employment (Ministry of Labor and Social Security (MLESS, 2020). This increment in migration is seen later followed by a high flow of remittance. Especially, in Middle East countries, the trend of migration and the inflow of remittance is seen at a profuse amount (Chettri et al., 2020).

In Nepal, since the decade-long insurgency came to a logical conclusion, people tended to live peacefully in the rural areas as previously. But, they had to earn their living and the barren land of the rural areas did not lay down any mechanisms of livelihood. So, to get rid of that problem they chose the path of foreign employment. However, they did not get sufficient institutional support from the government to start any venture then. That was because the government then was in the interim period for the drafting of the new constitution and in addition to that the lack of capital formation was also prevalent. So, for this, they migrated to earn outside the country. Thus, remittances began to flow in a profuse amount then. Since then, till today, remittance is said to occupy around 30 percent of the annual GDP (NRB, 2021). The economic determinants both micro and macro, have impacts on remittance, nonetheless, the macroeconomic determinants are taken so that the macroeconomic model could be established and the policy formation way out could be generalized.

2. Literature Review

The theoretical and empirical review has been administered to state several theories regarding the research process and to elucidate the important domains that are employed in this research.

2.1 Theoretical Review

Rapport, Hilel, Docquier, and Friederic (2005) stated that the theory that pertains to the remittance inflow is characterized by the Pure-Keynesian view in one of its oldest models that tries to capture the short-run macroeconomic impacts of the international transfers. Under the assumptions of the sticky prices and fixed exchange rates, the interest rate, consumption, and investment variables with the absence of the supply-side constraints lay down to comprehend the model. The model shows that any shock on the demand side contains a disproportionate effect on the national output. The Mundell-Flemming model is employed to research the short-run economy-wide consequences of the remittance within the Mundell-Flemming of an open economy with the ultimate prices and also the single composite good. During this framework, the effect of the international transfers on GDP depends on the assumptions made about the degree of capital mobility and charge per unit regime (Rapport et al., 2005).

The long-run view has been recognized that remittance affects the long-run performance of receiving economies in an exceedingly way that depends on whether the remittance is employed for consumption and investment. The theory prevails that the consumption from the remittance inflow goes to extend the consumption and eventually increases the worth level means the speed of inflation increases. The theories lay all the way down to the framework combining the short-run and therefore the long-run dynamics. Considering the theoretical perspective, the Remittance is obtained as:

$$Rem = f(Pe, Fer, Ir, C, I) \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

- where Rem = Remittance inflow
- Pe = Prices (sticky)
- Fer = Fixed rate of exchange
- Ir = Charge per unit
- C = Consumption
- I = Investment

The theoretical concept has been derived from the stated and established theories and on the premise of this, the empirical review is dispensed.

2.2 Empirical Review

Naufal (2007) conducted research on Remittances: determinants, motivation and effects with the major

objectives of examining the determinants, motivation and effects of the remittance inflow of the country and identifying the remitting behavior of the migrants in the country. The factors considered were households' income, remittance inflow, and level of education while the research methodology used was Utility function analysis with the income constraint equation and maximization on it and OLS regression analysis. The study found that working, residing in a developed country, and belonging to the nuclear family positively affect the remittances, the level of education and labor status affects the remittance inflows and the decision to participate in the remitting process appears to be positively related across the migrants.

Gaudel (2007) undertook a study on remittance income in Nepal: the need for economic development. The objectives of the study were to assess the relationship between remittance and economic growth in Nepal and to identify determinants of remittance affecting Nepal. The factors taken under study were foreign exchange rate, real GDP, remittances inflow, and BOP accounts. Using the OLS regression technique, Correlation analysis, and hypothesis testing, it was reported that remittance is found to be the major source of the foreign exchange rates; remittance has helped the Current account surplus in the BOP in Nepal and this is shown by the positive association as well as there was a positive relation between Remittances and the economic growth.

Hasan (2008) conducted research in Bangladesh on the macroeconomic determinants of remittances to examine the macroeconomic determinants of the worker's remittance in Bangladesh and to assess the model of the macroeconomic determinants with the factors identified. The factors considered were remittance inflow, domestic rate of interest, exchange rate, and GDP of host countries. The research methodology used was OLS regression with ADF (Augmented Dicky Fuller) unit root test, co-integration, and Granger Causality Test. The study found that macroeconomic determinants of the home and host countries have a significant impact on the home as well as host countries, inflation rates of Bangladesh have a negative relationship with the remittance inflow, and the host countries' GDP shows a positive relationship with remittance.

Lee, Hacker, and Singh (2009) conducted a study on determinants and macroeconomic impact on remittance in Sub-Saharan Africa. The main objectives of the study were to investigate the determinants and the macroeconomic role of remittance in Sub-Saharan Africa. The factors taken under consideration were M2/GDP, host income, expatriates, real exchange rates, and interest rate differentials. Using Distributed Lag Model and OLS regression, it was reported that remittances vary counter-

cyclically with variations in GDP per capita, consistent with the hypothesis that remittances can help mitigate economic shocks.

World Bank (2010) conducted research on micro impacts and macro determinants of remittances: a study of Albania with the objectives of identifying the micro impacts and macro determinants of the remittances in Albania as well as the decision making of the remittance-receiving households to the non-remittance receiving households. The factors taken under study were FDI, household consumption, remittance inflows, exports, and imports. Gravity type equation was used to assess the remittance flows in addition to the OLS regression technique. It was found that the remittance inflows show a significant contribution to the capital inflows of Albania. And the decision-making pattern of the remittance-receiving households on income spending is more than that of the non-remittance receiving households.

Nabi (2012) conducted research on an empirical inquiry into Macroeconomic determinants of remittance inflow in Bangladesh. The target of the study was to investigate macroeconomic determinants of remittances in Bangladesh. The factors taken into consideration were rate of exchange, rate of inflation, financial sector development, GDP, and stock of the workers abroad. Log-linear statistical method (OLS) method was employed for the study of variables. The findings suggested that inflation did not affect the Remittance flow in Bangladesh; currency depreciation promotes inward remittance in Bangladesh. The paper also prescribed policies that would help promote remittances inflows aiming at achieving higher growth, generation of employment, and alleviation of poverty.

Cerny (2015) conducted a study on determinants of remittances prices: evidence from 201 country corridors to identify the prices of the remittances on a global scale. The research methodology used for the study was OLS regression - time-series data. The factors taken under study were migrant stock, GDP, and bank A/C penetration. The findings of the study were that the non-linear effect of competition was seen among the remittance service providers and GDP per capita in sending and receiving countries on remittance price, and the negative effect on financial development on price was also confirmed.

Chettri et al. (2020) conducted a study on remittance and its impact on the Nepalese Economy to find the impact of remittance on the Nepalese economy. The research used the research methodology of trend analysis, bar diagram analysis, hypothesis testing, and regression analysis technique. The factors that were used for their study were remittance inflow, GDP, and inflation. The findings

of their study suggested that the percentage increase in inflation was lower in comparison with the proportion of remittance as compared with GDP, and there was also a positive and significant relationship found between GDP and remittance flow per year at a 10% level of significance.

3. Model Specification

This study was replicated by slightly adjusting the model given by Hasan (2008) who used the remittance as the dependent variable and the exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, and the GDP of host countries as the independent variables. However, this study omitted the variable GDP of host countries used by Hasan (2008) and included only three independent variables domestic rate of interest, inflation rate, and exchange rate. The host countries GDP from where the inflows of the remittances to Nepal from the top five foreign countries could not be assessed and Pant (2010) revealed that the GDP of the host countries of the remittance inflow to Nepal and the remittance inflow to Nepal is extremely correlated. Both of the variables reflect a similar trend and perfect multicollinearity. Upon which the inclusion of the GDP of the host countries as an independent variable would give insignificant results. Followed by a similar replication in this research, the GDP of the host country variable is ignored. The model of the research mainly concentrates on the three explanatory variables and one dependent variable.

The proposed model stands to be:

$$\log REM = \psi_1 \log EXC + \psi_2 \log INT + \psi_3 \log INF + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (2)}$$

where:

log = log of the original values-made the values in the percentage form (base 10).

$\psi_1, \psi_2,$ and ψ_3 = coefficients of the exchange rate, domestic rate of interest, and inflation rate respectively.

EXC = Exchange rate

INT = Domestic rate of interest (on savings)

INF = Inflation rate

REM = Remittance inflow

μ_t = The disturbance term (error term)

4. Data and Methodology

This study is based on the annual time series data from 1993 to 2019 which encompassed the data after the post-economic liberalization policy adopted in Nepal and before the pandemic of COVID 19 hit in Nepal. The Remittance inflow (REM) is employed as a dependent variable which is the transfer of the money by a foreign worker to her/his home country or simply sending the

amount from one country to another via a medium. The remittance was considered and its inflow was determined by the macroeconomic indicators that are released by the Nepal Rastra Bank on the yearly basis. The inflation rate (INF) used in the study is the rate at which the value of the commodities/services rises a year which refers to the decrement in the value of the money. The rate is obtained by the yearly projections by the central bank in its monetary policy frameworks and is updated every quarter. The domestic interest rate (INT) used in the study is the amount charged, expressed as a percentage of the principal, by a lender to the borrower. The domestic interest is the interest rate that is prevalent within the country and its ceiling is stated by the Monetary Policy as per the regulations or directives by the central bank of any economy. Likewise, in this study, the exchange rate (nominal) was used in Nepalese Rupees which was the exchange rate unit of Nepalese rupees for one U.S dollar. Due to the limitations of data the sample size (n) could not be taken at a profuse amount. The data was simply taken from the websites of the Nepal Rastra Bank, Ministry of Finance, and National Planning Commission.

The Time Series Inferential Research Design was used and the Johansson co-integration test was carried out to assess the long-run causal relationship between the Remittance inflow and the inflation rate, exchange rate, and domestic interest rate by the methodology mentioned by Harris (1995). The trace and maximum Eigenvalues statistics were observed and the results were analyzed. Before that, the time series data was tested with the Unit root test under the mechanism of the Augmented Dicky Fuller test and Phillip Perron test (Enders, 2017). All of the variables were stationary at I(1). As suggested by Johnston and DiNardo (2000), the residuals obtained by the ordinary least squares on the I(0) data are to be tested with the ADF and PP test to state whether there existed the long run causal relationship or not. Thereafter, the Johansson test of Co integration and the Vector Error Correction Model was employed to correct any shortcomings in the base model. Before the Co integration, as suggested by Lutekephol (2005) the Vector Auto Regression (VAR) was carried out to assess the best-suited lags taken for the study. As suggested by Gutierrez et al. (2009), the use of the Akaike Information Criteria is best suited and this research also uses Akaike's Information criteria is relevant and the lags having the lowest of the AIC value are selected as the appropriate lag length. The VAR (P) model was developed for all the equations. The three independent variables VAR models to test co-integration for the full period are presented in Equation 3:

$$\ln REM = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \phi_i \ln REM_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^2 \phi_j \ln INT_{t-j} + \sum_{m=1}^2 \phi_m \ln EXC_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^2 \phi_n \ln INF_{t-n} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation(3)}$$

These are the full period's VAR (P) models to test the co-integration for the full period in Equation 3. Under this the null hypothesis of no co integration $\phi_i = \phi_j = \phi_m = \phi_n = 0$ is tested against the alternative of cointegration $\phi_i \neq \phi_j \neq \phi_m \neq \phi_n \neq 0$.

This study used the vector error correction model (VEC) model, as given the Equations:

$$\Delta \ln REM = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \phi_i \ln REM_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^2 \phi_j \ln INT_{t-j} + \sum_{m=1}^2 \phi_m \ln EXC_{t-m} + \sum_{n=1}^2 \phi_n \ln INF_{t-n} + \rho_1 \mu_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation(4)}$$

The ρ_1 is the error correction term to state that the on which basis the system is converging towards the equilibrium. In this study the VEC model was employed because the VAR (P) model was developed as mentioned above for the co-integration test and once the test of the co-integration is found to be significant or there is co-integrating relationship among the variables the Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VEC) is used. The VECM (Vector Error Correction Model) is developed into the lag of p -1 meaning thereby that the Vector Error Correction Model is differentiated from a VAR model containing of one less lag order. For the Diagnostic and Stability test post building the long run model, the Breush Pagan

Heteroscedasticity test, BG LM Serial Correlation test, Jarque Bera Test for normal distribution, and CUSUM sum of squares test was carried out (Gujrati, 2013).

4. Empirical Results

To apply the co-integration technique the first step is to determine the order of the integration of each variable taken under study. This is because the co-integration technique can only be used in the order of integration of the variable is one, that is, I(1). The Augmented Dicky Fuller test and Phillip Perron test have been employed for this purpose both at the level and at the difference of the variables. The lag length used for the study is determined according to Akaike Information Criterion. The statistical results of the ADF tests and PP tests on intercept are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of ADF and PP test

Augmented Dicky Fuller test					Phillip Perron test				
Variables	Order of integration	p-value	Results						
log REM	I (0)	0.9348	I (1)	0.0039*	I (0)	0.4026	I (1)	0.0039*	Stationary
log INT	I (0)	0.1796	I (1)	0.0270#	I (0)	0.1814	I (1)	0.0002*	at 1st
log EXC	I (0)	0.7845	I (1)	0.0004*	I (0)	0.7845	I (1)	0.0004*	Difference
log INF	I (0)	0.1487	I (1)	0.0001*	I (0)	0.1429	I (1)	0.0001*	

Note: * and # denote the statistical significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Table 1 shows that all variables are stationary at the first difference in the intercept and constant with no trend. The Johansson co-integration is best suited to use since all the variables are of I(1).

The first stage of cointegration is accomplished by appropriate lag selection for the study. The VAR method was employed at first at arbitrary number lags to a maximum of 3 lags. Table 2 shows the lag selection criteria.

Table 2. Statistics for selecting the lag order

Number of lags Tested	Akaike Information Criterion	Results
1 Lag	-8.654521	2 lags
2 Lags	-9.121436	taken for the
3 Lags	-8.504572	Study

Table 2. denotes the clear depiction that the model on the 2 lags the AIC value was found the lowest when tested with the three lags since the AIC value was found to be lowest. With this, the number of lags used for the Johansson co-integration and in the Vector Error Correction Mechanism was based on the 2 lags optimum.

The existence of the long-run co-integrating relationship was tested out with the help of the residuals test. The residual was obtained from running the ordinary least squares regression on the dependent and independent variables. The Ordinary least Squares (OLS) was run between dependent and independent variables, and the error term (μ_t) was obtained as RESID — the error term that must be stationary at the level. The Unit root was tested using the Augmented Dicky-Fuller and Phillip-Perron tests. Table 3 denotes the clear depiction of it.

Table 3. Residuals test depiction of long-run cointegration

Augmented Dicky-Fuller test			Phillip-Perron test		Results
Variable	Order of integration	p-value	Order of integration	p-value	The error term is stationary at level
RESID	I (0)	0.0283*	I (0)	0.0370*	

Note: * denotes the statistical significance at the 5% level.

Table 3 is stated to be a significant position to have a long-run co-integration relationship because the residuals are stationary at their level signifying that the dependent and independent variables possess a long-run relationship.

After the appropriate lag length selection, the residuals test and the Johansson Co-Integration test were assessed and the result of the Johansson test with the 2 lags on the intercept only not in trend is obtained in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of Johansson Co integration test

Number of co-integrating equations	Eigenvalues	Trace statistics	Critical values	p-value	Results
None is co Integrated	0.733965	64.856	47.856	0.0006*	
At most two co Integrated	0.237264	9.3341	15.494	0.3354	Two co-integrating equation

Note: * denote the statistical significance at 1%.

The null hypothesis of no co-integration was rejected because the p-value (0.006) became less than 5 percent. The Eigenvalues and the trace statistics reveal that the critical values were greater than the trace statistics and also that the p-values (0.3354) became greater than 5 percent. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted which is there are at most two co-integrating equations. Due to the long-run co-integrating equation obtained the Vector error correction mechanism (VECM) was used for further analysis.

The vector error correction mechanism helps to assess the error-correcting term that converges towards the equilibrium. The long-run equilibrium was also obtained from the analysis. The VECM was run with the 2 lags and the software automatically subtracted one lag because it was different from the vector autoregression, and the lag of the order one less was used. The system of the equations was obtained from the VECM, and they were run under the least-squares method. Running this equation, the following results were obtained.

Table 5. Vector Error Correction Estimate

Coefficient's name	CoefficientC (1)	t statistic	Standard Error	p-value	Results
ECT	-0.723	-2.707255	0.267313	0.017*	ECT is correcting toward equilibrium

Note: * denote the statistical significance at the 5 % level.

Table 5 states that the error correction term became negative and significant (as the p-value was less than 5 %). The negative ECT (as -0.723) signifies that the equilibrium was converging towards the equilibrium at 72.3 percent every year, taking 1.38 ($=1/0.723$) years to fully converge the system towards the equilibrium.

With this, the evaluation of estimates was carried along with the long-run equation. This study obtained the long-run equation after applying the error correction mechanism. The sign of the coefficients of the equations changed, and the model was adjusted as:

$$REM = 4.3 - 1.27 * INT + 3.36 * EXC + 1.07 * INF.. Equation (5)$$

Equation 5, is the long-run equation obtained which signified the negative relationship between the remittance inflow and the domestic rate of interest, which means when the inflow of the remittance surges or declines by 1 percent the domestic rate of interest increases or decreases by 1.27 percent. In the same way, the remittance inflow and the exchange rate showed a positive relationship, which means, that when there is an increase or decrease with the 1 percent in the remittance inflow, the exchange rate increases or decreases by 3.36 percent. Likewise, when there is an increase or decrease in the 1 percent in the remittance inflow to Nepal, the inflation in the country increases or decreases by 1.07 percent. The assessment of the equation seemed quite vivid to state that the remittance inflow has much impact on the inflation dynamics in Nepal with this research phenomenon in the long run.

For the diagnostic and stability tests following tests were conducted:

■ The Breusch Godfrey Serial Correlation Lagrange Multiplier Test

The BG LM test was applied for the residual tests. The Chi-square probability value (p-value) of the test (as 0.7953) was greater than the critical value at the 5

percent level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis, of no serial correlation, was accepted within the model within the residuals obtained from the long-run analysis.

■ The Breusch Pagan Godfrey Heteroscedasticity Test

Similarly, this study applied the BP-Godfrey heteroscedasticity test to the residuals to check the volatility of the residuals. From the test, however, the Chi-square probability value (p-value) of the test (as 0.4611) was greater than the critical value at a 5 % level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis, of no heteroscedasticity in the model in the residuals from the long-run analysis, was accepted.

■ Jarque Bera test of the Normality

This study also applied the JB test for the normality of the residuals obtained. From the test, the residuals were found to be normally distributed. The Chi-Square probability value (p-value) of the test (as 0.967) was greater than the critical value at a 5 % level of significance. The null hypothesis, of non-normal distribution within the model in the residuals from the long-run analysis, was accepted.

■ The Cumulative Sums Control Chart (CUSUM) sum of Squares test for the Stability

The CUSUM sum of squares chart plots the cumulative sums of the deviations of every sample value from the target value of its recursive residuals. The CUSUM sum of squares test was carried out to assess the stability/soundness of the model and to see whether the method variations were in check during this research. During this research, the CUSUM sum of squares test was found to be stable. The model had structural stability because the cumulative sums of the recursive residuals were under the bracket of the 5 % level of significance. Hence, the long-run model obtained from the analysis became stable.

■ Non-Spuriousness of the Model

Because the value obtained of the coefficient of the determination (R^2) (as 0.5002) was lesser than the Durbin Watson value (DW Stat) (as 1.64), the model seemed non-spurious, in step with the reference taken from the Granger and Newbold (1974).

5. Conclusion

The remittance inflow to Nepal was obtained to have a long-run causal relation with the independent variables. There was a positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables except for the domestic rate of interest. When Remittance inflow is increased by 1 percent there increased the domestic interest rate on savings decreased by 1.27 percent. As the remittance increases the money income also increases thereby increasing the money in the hands of the people. More the money in the hand of the people, more the people tend to save and NPC (2012) reveals that 60 % of the remittance income is spent on consumption items and people merely spend 3 % on capital formation. With this, the deposit with this the bank and financial Institution (BFIs) does not increase to that amount so provide lucrative interest rates on savings also decrease.

The linkage of the remittance inflow seems to be positive with the exchange rate. One percent increase in the remittance inflow increases the exchange rate by 3.82 percent. This means there is foreign currency appreciation and the depreciation of the home/domestic currency. The exchange rate through substitution and wealth effects seem to influence the level of the remittance inflow. In a situation of currency depreciation, the goods in the home

country become less expensive and thus the migrants do not need to send back as much money as before for purchasing a given amount of goods and services from their families. This enables the migrants to substitute some goods in the home country for some more expensive goods in the country of residence. This is known as the substitution effect. On the other side, a devaluation or depreciation of the home country's exchange rate enables its migrant citizens to accumulate more wealth, which provides incentives to send back more money to buy even more goods including building a residence and investing in Real Estate homes country. This is the wealth effect of the exchange rate devaluation or depreciation (Chamon, Marcos, Sembalt, & Morant, 2005). This appears that the exchange rate is positively related to the remittance inflow. The remittance seems to be positively linked with the rate of inflation. If the remittance inflow would be increased or decreased by 1 percent, then the rate of inflation would also be increased or decreased by 1.07 percent. Most of the remittance income seems to be spent on consumption and then on the repayment of the loans. Around 60 % of the remittance inflow seems to be spent on consumption-related goods and services. This signifies that when people have more money in their hands they seem to spend more which eventually leads to the flow of the excess amount of money in the market and the demand for the goods and services surges up. When the demands for the goods and services are only there but the production process cannot be enhanced to that extent then the price of the goods and the services appear to increase due to the shortage of it. The equilibrium seems to finally converge at a point within 1.38 years in the long run from its short-run distortions. This seems to define that with the three independent variables interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate in relationship with the remittance inflow as a dependent variable the short-term disequilibrium can converge fully into the equilibrium within 1.38 years. In the context of Nepal, the system with the above variables appears to be quite fair because of the lag of the effect of the variables on the mainstream economy. Here, the lags are obtained as two lags from the lag selection criteria, which is the average lag for all the variables to lay down their respective effect on the economy. With it, the system is fairly creating a long-term equilibrium after short-term fluctuations in a time range that seems to be easy to cope with in the case of our country.

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Mr. Aditya Pokhrel is a young and dynamic persona who serves as an Assistant Director of Nepal Rastra Bank (central bank) since March 12, 2021. He holds a Master's Degree in Business Administration (distinction) from Kathmandu Don Bosco College, Purbanchal University and a Master's Degree in Economics (distinction) from Ratna Rajya Laxmi Campus, Tribhuvan University. Mr. Pokhrel has published several articles in national daily and in NRB Bulletins including its half yearly, and yearly papers.